

On the Study of Co-separation of Thorium and Rare Earths with Calcium Sulphate on a Tracer Scale

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Co-precipitation of thorium (UX_2) and rare earths (Ce^{144} , Pm^{147} , Eu^{152} , Eu^{154} , and Y^{91}) with calcium sulphate has been investigated. Thorium and rare-earth tracers are taken up through mixed crystal formation by an unstable form of calcium sulphate which subsequently turns out to stable monoclinic gypsum. The range of mixed crystal formation in all these cases is, however, very narrow. When the concentration of the tracer ion exceeds that range, the uptake obeys an adsorption isotherm. It has been found that the presence of one rare earth, the concentration of which is just beyond the range of mixed crystal formation, causes the uptake of another rare earth (in tracer concentration) to obey the Freundlich adsorption isotherm. Uptake of yttrium and thorium, however, differs in this respect from that of rare earths. These two in finite quantity do not exert any influence on the uptake of tracer rare earths and *vice versa*. A comparative study of the λ values for different rare earths indicates that mixed crystal formation in these cases is through double-salt formation.

It is well known that calcium fluoride forms mixed crystals with rare earth and thorium fluorides¹⁻³. It has also been shown⁴ that one of the hydrates of calcium oxalate carries rare earths through mixed crystal formation. The question naturally arises as to how far the uptake of rare earths and thorium by calcium compounds can be generalised. Further study in this line brings in calcium sulphate as a host component. The system is interesting in the sense that calcium sulphate is known to exist in different morphological modifications, the stabilities of which are characterised by definite transition temperatures. A recent study⁵ on calcium sulphate system points out that the transitions between different morphological forms in aqueous solution may be represented as follows:

If there is any uptake of rare earths and thorium by calcium sulphate, it is then interesting to study whether there is any evidence of mixed crystal formation or the process is due only to adsorption. In the former case, it will be interesting to study whether it is restricted to one particular form of calcium sulphate or it embraces all varieties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents were all of AnalaR quality. Y^{91} , Eu^{152} , Eu^{154} , Ce^{144} , and Pm^{147} , used in this investigation, were supplied by A. E. R. E. Harwell, England. Carrier-free Y^{91} was

1. Zintl and Ugdard, *Z. anorg. Chem.*; 1939, 240, 150.
2. Ketelaar and Willems, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1937, 56, 29.
3. Khlopin and Merkulova, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, USSR*, 1949, 65, 861; 1950, 71, 689.
4. Purkayastha and Bhattacharyya, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 10, 103.
5. d'Ans *et al.*, *Kolloid U. Steinsalz*, 1955, No. 9, 17.

supplied as chloride in hydrochloric acid medium of 99% radio-chemical purity. When the concentration of yttrium in our observations is referred, the concentration of inactive yttrium as present in the supplier's sample was taken into consideration. Eu^{152} and Eu^{154} were prepared by (n, γ) reaction on natural europium of spectroscopically pure quality as supplied by Messrs Johnson & Mathey. Carrier-free Ce^{144} and Pm^{147} were prepared from fission products and were supplied as chloride in hydrochloric acid medium of 99% radio-chemical purity. UX_1 was used in the investigation as a tracer for thorium. It was prepared from an aged uranyl nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) solution, using calcium oxalate⁶ as carrier for UX_1 . Calcium was later removed by scavenging out UX_1 with $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$. Iron was subsequently removed by continuous extraction with isopropyl ether. Stable tracers like yttrium, europium, cerium, and thorium were of spectroscopically pure quality as supplied by Messrs Johnson & Mathey.

Co-crystallisation of Rare Earth and Thorium with Calcium Sulphate.—To a solution of calcium chloride of known concentration a known amount of tracer under investigation was added. The acidity of the solution was adjusted to about 1N with HCl. Different amounts of H_2SO_4 ($\approx 2N$) were then added, supersaturation was eliminated by stirring, and the calcium sulphate formed was filtered immediately. The amounts of calcium sulphate precipitated were estimated⁷ as CaSO_4 and the activities remaining in solution were measured by means of thin-walled glass liquid counters. In the case of Pm^{147} , the measurement of activity from solid samples was necessary (Table V). The distribution coefficients⁸, D and λ , were calculated as follows.

$$\left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solid}} = D \left(\frac{\text{Tracer}}{\text{Carrier}} \right)_{\text{solution}}$$

$$\log \frac{\text{Initial tracer}}{\text{Tracer in solution}} = \lambda \log \frac{\text{Initial carrier}}{\text{Carrier in solution}}$$

In order to obtain a homogeneous distribution of the tracer into the carrier lattice, the calcium sulphate, thus precipitated, was shaken for a long period.

TABLE I

Co-separation of europium (Eu^{152} & 154) with calcium sulphate at diff. temp.

Initial conc. of $\text{Eu} = 4.54 \times 10^{-7}M$. Initial conc. of $\text{Ca} = 3.49 \times 10^{-1}M$.

%Ca. pptd.	%Europium (Eu^{152} & 154) co-pptd.	λ .	D .
A. Temp. = 35° (Gypsum).			
21.4	12.3	0.54	0.51
39.3	24.9	0.59	0.53
44.6	29.8	0.60	0.53
47.0	30.4	0.57	0.49
65.9	46.4	0.58	0.45
67.0	47.3	0.58	0.44
73.0	50.6	0.54	0.39
		Av. 0.57	

6. Purkayastha and Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 427.

7. Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II, John Wiley, New York, 1955, p. 245.

8. Wahl and Bonner, "Radioactivity Applied to Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1951, p. 106.

TABLE I (contd.)

%Ca. pptd.	%Europium (Eu ¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴) co-pptd.	λ .	D.
B. Temp. = 72° (Anhydrite)			
19.6	37.3	2.27	2.61
31.9	55.1	2.00	2.62
40.0	62.7	1.03	2.51
51.7	71.2	1.71	2.31
56.2	73.5	1.61	2.16
62.5	77.7	1.53	2.09
C. Temp. = 98° (Hemihydrate).			
4.5	18.9	4.59	4.99
43.7	64.0	1.78	2.29
46.2	63.6	1.68	2.12
50.2	66.1	1.53	1.94

TABLE II

Co-separation of europium (Eu¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴) with calcium sulphate after attainment of equilibrium between the solid and the solution phases.

Initial conc. of Eu and Ca are the same as in Table I. Temp. = 35°.

% Co-pptd.	..	14.9	30.0	48.4	59.0	68.3
%Eu co-pptd.	..	11.0	18.8	25.2	27.8	32.9
λ	..	0.73	0.36	0.44	0.37	0.35
D	..	0.71	0.51	0.36	0.27	0.23

TABLE III

Co-separation of europium (Eu¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴) with calcium sulphate at varying europium-ion conc.

Initial conc. of Ca = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$. Temp. = 35°.

Initial Eu conc.	%Ca pptd.	%Eu co-pptd.	λ .	D.
A. $5.68 \times 10^{-7} M$	23.6	15.7	0.63	0.60
	44.5	29.7	0.60	0.53
	51.9	33.6	0.56	0.47
	69.4	50.1	0.59	0.44
			Av. 0.59	
B. $3.00 \times 10^{-6} M$	29.8	17.4	0.54	0.50
	68.4	48.2	0.57	0.43
			Av. 0.55	
C. $8.35 \times 10^{-6} M$	23.8	13.0	0.52	0.48
	45.4	27.6	0.53	0.46
	57.4	37.8	0.56	0.45
	65.9	43.6	0.54	0.40
	73.4	50.2	0.53	0.35
			Av. 0.54	

TABLE III (contd.)

Initial Eu conc.	%Ca pptd.	%Eu co-pptd.	λ .	D.
D. $3.19 \times 10^{-5} M$	29.5	17.1	0.54	0.49
	38.7	23.8	0.56	0.49
	47.0	29.7	0.56	0.48
	61.9	39.5	0.52	0.40
	67.8	43.3	0.50	0.36
			Av. 0.54	
E. $7.99 \times 10^{-5} M$	24.3	13.3	0.51	0.43
	39.4	22.1	0.50	0.44
	59.3	33.9	0.46	0.35
	72.1	42.1	0.43	0.28
F. $3.15 \times 10^{-4} M$	10.9	4.8	0.43	0.41
	33.8	15.9	0.42	0.37
	57.5	27.6	0.38	0.28
G. $1.57 \times 10^{-3} M$	22.2	9.1	0.38	0.36
	38.7	15.4	0.34	0.29
	59.3	23.4	0.29	0.21

TABLE IV

*Co-separation of cerium (ous) with calcium sulphate at 35°.*Initial Ce conc. = $2.76 \times 10^{-7} M$. Initial Ca conc. = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$.

%Ca pptd.	..	28.2	40.9	57.8	64.8	70.9
%Ce ¹⁴⁴ co-pptd.	..	22.6	34.6	50.4	54.8	59.8
λ	..	0.774	0.808	0.813	0.764	0.738 (Av. 0.779)
D	..	0.745	0.765	0.742	0.664	0.610

TABLE V*

*Co-separation of promethium (Pm¹⁴⁷) with calcium sulphate at 35°.*Initial Ca conc. = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$.

%Ca pptd.	%Pm ¹⁴⁷ co-pptd.		λ			D		
	(a)	(b)	(a).	(b).	Mean.	(a).	(b).	Mean.
29.5	21.7	22.1	0.700	0.715	0.708	0.662	0.678	0.670
36.4	27.1	27.4	0.724	0.733	0.729	0.678	0.689	0.694
47.6	38.9	38.4	0.762	0.749	0.756	0.701	0.686	0.694
52.9	41.1	43.8	0.703	0.765	0.734	0.621	0.694	0.658
60.5	47.4	49.3	0.692	0.731	0.712	0.588	0.635	0.612
67.5	53.2	55.3	0.676	0.726	0.701	0.547	0.608	0.578
					Av. 0.723			

*Distribution of Pm¹⁴⁷ activity between the solid and the liquid phases was measured by the method of isotopic dilution, using $\text{CaC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ as the scavenger. This method has been developed by us⁶. 'a' and 'b' indicate the measurements done from the liquid and the solid phases respectively.

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TABLE VI

Co-separation of yttrium (Y³⁺) with calcium sulphate at diff. yttrium-ion conc.
 Conditions same as in Table III.

Initial Y conc.	%Ca pptd.	%Y ³⁺ co-pptd.	λ .	λ_p^* .	D.
A. $1.72 \times 10^{-7} M$	29.3	4.17	0.122	0.117	0.105
	32.6	5.82	0.151		
	42.0	7.44	0.138		
	56.1	10.50	0.140		
	64.0	12.60	0.134		
	68.6	15.00	0.140		
			Av. 0.137		0.081
B. $1.72 \times 10^{-6} M$	27.7	3.87	0.121	0.119	0.105
	38.1	6.65	0.148		
	44.2	7.25	0.129		
	67.3	15.10	0.147		
			Av. 0.136		
C. $1.72 \times 10^{-5} M$	27.8	4.21	0.131	0.130	0.114
	44.1	8.16	0.146		
	66.6	13.90	0.137		
			Av. 0.138		
D. $1.72 \times 10^{-3} M$	29.7	5.11	0.149		0.128
	43.7	5.43	0.097		
	63.2	8.24	0.086		
E. $1.03 \times 10^{-2} M$	21.0	3.98	0.171		0.156
	38.2	6.64	0.142		
	60.2	10.90	0.124		

* λ_p represents some values of the logarithmic distribution constant, λ , computed from the activity measurements from the solid phases.

TABLE VII

Co-separation of thorium (UX₁) by calcium sulphate at 35°

Initial Th conc. = $2.55 \times 10^{-9} M$. Initial Ca conc. = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$.

%Ca pptd.	%Th (UX ₁) co-pptd.	λ .	D.	
44.0	21.7	0.423	0.353	
47.8	24.3	0.426	0.351	
54.0	29.3	0.436	0.341	
A	64.5	35.2	0.410	0.299
	69.0	37.4	0.307	0.299
		Av. 0.420		
27.7	13.0	0.432	0.392	
45.8	23.4	0.435	0.361	
B*	57.2	28.5	0.397	0.299
	68.1	36.6	0.399	0.271
		Av. 0.416		

*In experiments (B) aged uranium solution (containing 2.87 mg. uranium per ml) served as the source of UX₁.

TABLE VIII

Co-separation of europium with calcium sulphate in presence of weighable amounts (above the range of mixed crystal formation) of cerium (ous), yttrium, and thorium at 35°.
Initial Eu conc. = $4.55 \times 10^{-7} M$. Initial Ca conc. = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$.

Initial conc.	%Ca pptd.	%Eu co-pptd.	λ .	D.
A. Ce: $2.78 \times 10^{-4} M$	30.2	19.4	0.600	0.556
	38.6	23.4	0.547	0.486
	47.3	27.8	0.509	0.439
	52.4	28.7	0.456	0.366
	60.5	33.0	0.431	0.322
B. Y: $1.72 \times 10^{-4} M$	31.7	17.9	0.518	0.470
	47.7	30.5	0.561	0.481
	53.5	34.9	0.561	0.466
	60.0	39.2	0.530	0.414
	67.1	42.4	0.496	0.361
		Av. 0.533		
C. Th: $2.57 \times 10^{-5} M$	34.3	17.8	0.467	0.412
	48.2	28.4	0.508	0.426
	53.0	31.8	0.494	0.399
	62.8	37.3	0.472	0.352
	72.8	46.5	0.480	0.325
		Av. 0.484		

TABLE IX

Co-separation of thorium (UX_1) with calcium sulphate in presence of weighable amounts (above the range of mixed crystal formation) of europium and yttrium at 35°.
Initial Th conc. = $2.57 \times 10^{-8} M$. Initial Ca conc. = $3.49 \times 10^{-1} M$.

% Ca pptd.	% Th (UX_1) co-pptd.	λ .	D.
(a) Initial Eu conc. = $1.26 \times 10^{-4} M$.			
24.8	9.53	0.351	0.320
30.8	11.20	0.324	0.284
45.5	19.70	0.362	0.294
50.1	22.40	0.364	0.287
53.2	23.90	0.360	0.276
60.8	29.80	0.381	0.277
60.9	31.30	0.397	0.290
66.5	31.70	0.349	0.234
67.6	35.70	0.392	0.243
		Av. 0.364	
(b) Initial Y conc. = $1.72 \times 10^{-4} M$.			
23.3	9.60	0.380	0.350
32.4	13.20	0.362	0.317
41.9	19.60	0.402	0.338
50.1	25.20	0.418	0.336
58.6	28.50	0.380	0.282
67.1	32.70	0.356	0.238
		Av. 0.383	

TABLE X*

Co-separation of europium with potassium sulphate at 35°.
Initial Eu conc. = $4.55 \times 10^{-7} M$. Initial K_2SO_4 conc. = $1.80 \times 10^{-1} M$.

% K_2SO_4 pptd.	Eu ¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴ co-pptd.	λ .	D.
28.1	77.0	4.46	8.53
39.2	83.4	3.01	7.80
A 60.0	92.0	2.75	7.63
65.7	93.3	2.53	7.38
80.1	95.7	1.93	5.60
38.8	57.0	1.76	2.17
B 57.0	70.5	1.44	1.80
71.1	75.8	1.14	1.27

*Potassium sulphate was precipitated in presence of Eu¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴ by the addition of EtOH to a solution of K_2SO_4 in a total volume of 25 ml while the solution was being continuously stirred. 'A' indicates those studies where the precipitate was immediately separated and 'B' indicates those where the separation of the solid and liquid phases was done after allowing the precipitate to be shaken in its mother liquor for 24 hours.

DISCUSSION

The uptake of rare earths by calcium sulphate has been studied at different temperatures (Table I) with the help of Eu¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴ tracer. Table I(A) shows that when calcium sulphate is crystallised at 35°, the uptake of tracer (Eu¹⁵² & ¹⁵⁴) follows Doerner-Hoskins distribution law. But it is interesting to note that the uptake does not follow either the homogeneous or the heterogeneous distribution law when different fractions of calcium sulphate crystals, incorporated with tracer europium, are shaken at the same temperature (35°) in contact with the respective mother liquors for four days (Table II). In trial experiments it was found that a period of four days was sufficient for the attainment of equilibrium. The homogeneous distribution did not hold good; the results, however, followed a surface phenomenon, the data agreeing well with a Freundlich adsorption isotherm (Fig. 1). The fact that the heterogeneous distribution factor (λ) comes constant but the homogeneous distribution factor (D) affords discordant values clearly indicates that the freshly precipitated host lattice differs in morphology from that of the aged one. Such a behaviour has already been reported⁴. It appears that the rare earths are taken up by an unstable structure of calcium sulphate⁹⁻¹⁰ later on, turning into monoclinic gypsum which does not bear any morphological characteristic to carry any rare earth activity through mixed crystal formation. The same behaviour is observed with cerium (Ce¹⁴⁴), promethium (Pm¹⁴⁷), yttrium (Y⁹¹), and thorium (UX₁) with the difference that each system is characterised by a logarithmic distribution coefficient of its own (Tables IV-VII). Some distribution studies were also made at temperatures where formation of anhydrite and hemihydrates was favoured. The heterogeneous distribution factor does not show the same characteristic as has been observed in the case of gypsum (Table I, B and C).

9. Davis, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1907, 26, 727.

10. Lambert and Schaffer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2648.

The effect of addition of increasing amounts of inactive rare earths or thorium on the mode of incorporation in calcium sulphate has been studied in some details and this brings forth many interesting aspects. On examining the values of the distribution coefficients, observed at different initial concentrations of the tracer ion (Tables III and VI), the constancy of the distribution factor is found to be dependent on the concentration of the tracer ion. When the initial concentration of the tracer is maintained sufficiently low, the incorporation takes place in the crystal lattice, obeying the heterogeneous distribution law, but when the concentration of the tracer component is increased sufficiently by addition of inactive components in question, the distribution law is not obeyed, emphasising that the incorporation in this region is not due to mixed crystal formation. Surface adsorption plays an important role (Fig. 2). Thus the mechanism of the uptake involved in finite dilution is not the same as that in tracer concentration.

FIG. 1. Isotherm on carrying of europium by calcium sulphate after shaking the system for four days.

z = amount of Eu carried (g./lit.); c = conc. of remaining Eu in soln. (g./lit.); m = amount of Ca (g./lit.) precipitated as sulphate. (Vide Table II)

FIG. 2. Isotherm on the uptake of rare earths and thorium by calcium sulphate in the region of conc. of the guest component where λ values slope down (vide Fig. 3).

z = amount of rare earths or Th carried (g./lit.); c = conc. of rare earths or Th remaining in soln. (g./lit.); m = amount of Ca (g./lit.) precipitated as sulphate.

In order to study the effect of increasing amounts of stable tracer on the distribution factors, the same amount of calcium was taken. Almost the same quantity of calcium sulphate was precipitated in each case and all other operations were conducted under identical conditions. Only the concentration of the stable tracer was varied. When the observed distribution factors (λ) are plotted against respective concentrations of the tracer component, all the data fit in two straight lines meeting each other through a slight curvature (Fig. 3). The mixed crystal forming region is well defined, as is evident from λ vs. concentration curve, by a line running parallel to the x -axis. Beyond this region, the constancy of λ vanishes. The uptake represented by λ slopes down in a straight line as the amount of inactive constituents increases. The region, where the λ values slope down, has been found to obey adsorption isotherm (Fig. 2). The concentration corresponding to the furthest

right hand point of the line, parallel to the x -axis, should therefore be identified as the limit of mixed crystal formation. It is interesting to note here that the limits of mixed crystal formation, so observed in the case of rare earths such as cerium, europium, and yttrium, are similar. Thorium also shows the same characteristic though the limiting concentration in this case is slightly different.

FIG. 3 The range of mixed crystal formation of rare earths and Th with CaSO_4 at 35° . c = initial conc. (moles/litre) of the guest components (Ce, Eu, Y or Th).

The presence of yttrium or thorium in finite concentration does not affect the uptake of europium at tracer concentration (Table VIII, B and C). Presence of appreciable amounts of yttrium and europium also does not affect the uptake of thorium through mixed crystal formation (Table IX). It is therefore an indication that the guest ion in these cases are different. Inference can therefore be drawn that a rare earth, like europium, does not modify the property of yttrium or thorium present at tracer concentration in this system.

Fig. 4 shows that the λ values pass through a smooth curve as the ionic radius decreases. The position of yttrium is well defined, as is generally found in fractional crystallisation of the rare earths. The up-

FIG. 4. Relationship of distribution coefficient (λ) on the uptake of rare earths by CaSO_4 with the ionic radius¹³ (r) of the respective rare earths.

take of rare earths in such cases should go therefore through the formation of a double sulphate since the solubility of double sulphate decreases with the increase of ionic radii in the rare earth series. The solubilities of the simple sulphates follow, however, a zig zag path¹¹. This conclusion leads us to support the view that there is some relation between solubility and comparative uptake. Hahn¹² also attempted to arrive at a qualitative relationship between solubility and uptake. He pointed out that this relationship should be taken with reservation. This particular fact has been recently taken up by Fiebush *et al.*¹⁴. They chose in most of the cases the same host component and the guest component was also similar in chemical properties. Thus the uptake of different rare earths by cerous oxalate has been thoroughly studied and attempts have been made to correlate the λ values with the solubility of the oxalates in question. The relation is not strictly quantitative; it obeys, however, a qualitative order. The solubility is concluded to have some influence in such cases. Our finding that the uptake of rare earths by calcium sulphate takes place through double-salt formation has therefore got justification.

Hahn¹⁴ also came indirectly to the same conclusion that tracer lead was taken up by alkali halides through double-salt formation.

This finding led us to extend our studies towards the uptake of rare earths by alkali sulphates (Table X). The uptake, though considerably high, is not in accordance with distribution laws, but it follows a Freundlich adsorption isotherm. Inference can therefore be derived that no double sulphate of rare earths under experimental conditions forms mixed crystal with potassium sulphate.

Incidentally, the study of the distribution laws (Berthelot-Nernst and Doerner-Hokins) is of great importance in revealing the existence of unstable phases in the course of precipitation. A thorough study in different systems is expected to clarify the anomalies pointed out by Hahn, Chlopin, and other earlier workers^{8,12} in the process of co-separation.

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